

Comprehensive Microstructural Evaluation of E-Glass Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composites and Their Components

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Key Terms and Text: thermoset BMC, unsaturated polyester, composite recycling, microstructural characterization, automotive applications

Abstract: Half and quarter inch virgin E-glass chopped strand fibers were obtained and analyzed using optical and electron microscopy. They were found to have an average individual fiber diameter of 13.5 micron and a smooth surface. The quarter inch chopped strand had a much rougher end, which would suggest different chopping procedures. Recycled sheet molding compound was obtained from Mecelec, a French recycling company. This was found to have varying fiber diameters and lengths, good percent coating of resin, and surface roughness. The recyclate was also analyzed for change in surface roughness, dispersion, and integrity as well as interfacial surface tensions. The recyclate was combined with virgin materials in different ratios and composite bars molded using a Carver Flat Plate Press. These bars were broken using a three-point bending strength test. The broken bars were sectioned, sputtered, and then fractographically analyzed using optical and electron microscopy. The dominant failure mechanism of bars made with solely virgin chopped strand was found to be failure of the fiber-matrix interface indicated by fiber-matrix debonding, fibrillar crazing, and fiber pull-out. These bars exhibit good fiber to resin bonding and the large amounts of fiber allow for significant bridging which accounts for their high strength. This can be seen in the very jagged fracture surface, which is due to the plastic deformation failure; these bars fail at several unique crack origins that eventual branch together resulting in a slow crack propagation. Bars containing solely recyclate were found to have a more brittle failure mechanism. Once a crack appears, catastrophic failure ensues rapidly. There was much less fiber, less fiber bridging, and a high amount of resin pull-out. Radial cracking indicated good fiber to matrix bonding. Bars containing both recyclate and virgin fiber exhibited a combination fracture as expected. Failure originates around pieces of thermoplastic additive contained in the recyclate that act as inclusions.

I. Introduction

From the aerospace industry to the home, glass-reinforced composite materials can be seen in millions of products and their use is steadily increasing. In 2000, manufacturers in the United States shipped 3.9 billion pounds of composite materials, as estimated by The Composite Fabricators Association.¹ Polymer matrix composites are classified as either thermoplastic or thermosetting composites, the former is recyclable, the later, for the most part is not, at least not yet. Many composites today are made with thermoplastic matrices, which have a relatively simple method of recycling; they can be melted down and then reformed. However, when thermosets are heated, the materials become softer and may even combust or degrade, but will not assume a state that can be reformed. Most products containing a thermoset matrix will end up in non-biodegradable landfills, as there has been little progress in the area of their recycling.

Currently, there is only one method being used to recycle polymer thermoset composites commercially. In this method, the manufacturer grinds up recycled scrap and combines it with virgin materials to form a new composite. The majority of the research regarding recycled thermoset composite materials is in regards to the relationship between the amount of recyclate and the mechanical strength of the new composite. Studies show a general trend of decreasing structural and mechanical strength with

increasing recycle.⁴ A more scientific approach, one that examines these composites below the macroscopic level, will yield information regarding why the composites that contain recycled materials fail at a lower stress. The hypothesis is that the weakening is due to poor bonding between the recycle and the new resins. If in case this is true, composite strength should increase by improving the interfacial strength between the ground recycle and the virgin materials. The key to improving the interface is to understand the interactions between the recycled fibers and virgin resins; the first place to begin looking is at the microscale.

One of the most important parts of our microstructural analysis is fractography. Fractography is defined as the means and methods for characterizing a fractured specimen or component.⁵ It is the examination of fracture-exposed surfaces and the interpretation of crack patterns and fracture markings. Fractography can provide important information on location of fracture origins, direction of crack propagation, interactions with the crack front, crack development sequence, and the stress state at the time of fracture. Fracture markings include, but are not limited to, fracture origin, arrest lines, primary, secondary, and tertiary Wallner lines, fracture mirror, twist, wake, and velocity hackle, scarps, gull wings, and cantilever curls. Each of these features gives unique information about the failure mechanism of the material being investigated. The behavior of a composite material results from the shared properties of its constituent parts. In the case of glass fiber reinforced thermoset composites, the properties are those of the fiber, the polymer matrix, and the fiber-matrix interface. When a composite fractures, one would expect to see failure of the matrix, of the fibers, at the interface, or a combination of these. In the work presented, we used optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) for the microstructural analysis. The results of optical and SEM analysis gives important information regarding the make-up of virgin and scrap thermoset composite materials, their compatibility, response to mechanical granulation, strength, and their failure mechanisms. The information is important in shedding light on thermoset composite interactions and contributes to the ongoing research of finding affordable, efficient ways to recycle such materials.

II. Experimental Procedure

- a. **Materials:** Recycled SMC fibers were obtained from Mecerlec Composites Recyclage in France. Mecerlec's SMC recycle is made by grinding SMC waste using a proprietary crushing technique. The BMC formulations used were made in-house and were based on AOC Inc.'s T766 high reactivity isophthalic based polyester resin. To the resin AOC N714 polystyrene, styrene monomer (99%), and tert-butyl peroxybenzoate (TBPB) (98%) were added. The styrene was added as the crosslinker and the TBPB as the initiator, both were used as received from Aldrich. Zinc stearate from Aldrich was added to the resin as a mold release agent. The virgin fibers used were 1/2" and 1/4" Saint Gobain Vetrotex 97D(BMC) glass fibers sized for polyester and vinylester resins. Calcium carbonate (CaCO₃) from ACS International was used as filler for the BMC.
- b. **Sample Preparation**
 - i. **Composite formulations:** BMC containing virgin fibers and those with recycle fiber were batched according to the formulations in Table 1. Samples containing all 1/2" virgin fiber, a 50/50 by weight mixture of 1/2" and 1/4" virgin fibers, all 1/4" virgin fiber, and no fiber were made to set a baseline for comparison of BMCs containing recycle. In the BMC with all recycle, the virgin fiber was replaced 1 to 1 by weight with recycle.

Table 1: Weight Percent of Components Added to BMC Formulations

BMC Classification	Virgin fiber or Recyclate
Component	Weight percent (%)
T766	18.4
N 714	9.2
Styrene	3.1
TBPB	0.5
Zinc Stearate	1.8
CaCO ₃	50
Fiber or recyclate	16.7

ii. Composite fabrication

Composites were batched by adding the polyester resin, containing styrene crosslinker, with mold release agent and the initiator. Calcium carbonate and glass fiber were added to create a doughy prepreg. The prepreg was divided into 21.4 g log shaped charges approximately 100mm long and 13 mm in diameter. The charges were loaded directly into the mold. The mold was pressed at 150°C and 2600 psi for 2 minutes.

iii. Fractographic Preparation

Bars were broken using a three-point bending test on a Com-Ten instrument. The bars were then sectioned using a high-speed saw. Sectioning was done to analyze both fracture and crack surfaces.

1. Fracture Surfaces- The pressed bars were cracked during the three point bend test on the tensile side. By putting continued manual pressure on the opposite side of the crack, the bars were broken fully. They were then sectioned near the full break and mounted so that the fracture surface was visible.
2. Crack Surfaces- The pressed bars were taped around the crack and then sectioned on each side of it. The tape was then removed and the piece mounted so that the crack was visible.

c. Analysis

i. SEM The samples were mounted on studs, sputtered (Film-Vac Inc. Mini-Coater) using a 60% gold and 40% palladium coating. The coating for most surfaces was approximately 250Å. The scanning electron microscope used was an Amray 1810. The current was set to 20 keV, a vacuum was pulled on the sample chamber and a back-scattered mode was used. Some charging was a problem with the virgin fiber fracture surfaces as they were very jagged and the gold-palladium coating could not reach all the recesses.

ii. Optical Microscopy As-received materials were analyzed using a Leitz Laborlux Optical Microscope. The crack and fracture surface were optically analyzed using an M32 Wild Heerbrugg (Switzerland) microscope with a Fiber-Lite High Intensity Illuminator (Dolan-Jenner Industris, Inc.).

III. Results and Discussion

As-Received Materials: First, the as-received materials including ½ and ¼ inch chopped fibers and recyclate were examined using both optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The ½ inch and ¼ inch chopped fibers both had an average individual fiber diameter of ~13.5 microns. The fibers were

received as strands, or fiber bundles. There were typically more fibers present in the quarter inch chopped strand which had a width between 0.65 mm and 0.7 mm, while the half inch strand had an average width around 0.6 mm. The quarter inch chopped strand had a much rougher end, which would suggest that the chopping procedure may have been different (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Image A is fiber from the recyclate showing random orientation, diameter, and length. Image B is half inch chopped strand (left) and quarter inch chopped strand (right) showing similar orientation, diameter, and length. Leitz Laborlux Optical Microscope.

The recycled material received from Mecerlec was examined using both optical microscopy and SEM. The recycled sheet-molding compound (SMC) was made of fibers and large pieces of two different colored resins: black and white. Figure 2 shows the SEM micrographs of the black and white resin surfaces. The black resin surface seemed to be mostly matrix and grooves from pulled-out fibers, while the white resin showed much less surface roughness and a bit more fiber content. The fibers in the white piece are also much longer and have a more uniform distribution compared to those in the black resin. They also have a range of 5-90% resin coating shown in Figure 3. Fiber lengths in the recyclate material ranged from 1/8" to 2/3" in length.

Figure 2. SEM images of Mecerlec recycled sheet-molding compound, A) shows the rough surface of black resin piece and B) shows the smooth surface of white resin piece B.

Figure 3. SEM photo of Meelec recycle white resin piece showing large range of resin coating and fiber lengths.

Composite Systems: Virgin and recycled composite bars were fractured using 3-point bending. The recycled bars exhibited a straight and flat crack propagation, which was connected across the entire surface while the virgin bars exhibited a crack propagation of about 45 degrees. In Figure 4, one can compare the fracture surface of bars containing no reinforcement, bars containing recycle, and bars containing virgin reinforcement. The degree of jaggedness of the surface increases as the strength of the composite increases. Fracture features such as fiber pull-out, fiber-matrix debonding, and fiber and matrix fracture seemed to be fairly similar in all the samples. However, the virgin fiber bars were distinguishable having a rougher fracture surface, no matrix pull-out, more matrix fracture, and higher percent coating coverage of the fibers. Matrix pull-out is defined as large portions of resin in a heterogeneous composite fracturing at the interface between new and old resin, which was consistently seen in the recycled composites. SEM micrographs of a virgin composite made with 1/4" fiber are provided in Figure 5 showing the amount of fiber surface coverage with resin. When comparing the fiber behavior in the composites (virgin versus recycled), little difference was found. Both exhibited good bonding with the new, virgin resin. Figure 6 shows the SEM micrograph at a higher resolution for 1/4 inch virgin fiber reinforced composite with good resin to fiber bonding. The images in Figure 7 show a much lower fiber content in the bars containing recycle. The reason for the lower fiber content for composites containing recycle is due to formulation issues and is revisited in a latter section of this paper.

A) B) C)
 Figure 4. Optical micrographs comparing the fracture surfaces of composite bars containing A) no reinforcement, B) recycle reinforcement, and C) virgin fiber reinforcement. The jaggedness of the fracture surface increases with strength due to fiber bridging effects.

Figure 5. 1/4" virgin fiber composite fracture surface showing good fiber surface coverage with resin.

A) B)

Figure 6. SEM micrograph of 1/4" virgin fiber composite. A strong resin to fiber bond, image B, eventually results in matrix tearing, image A, at the interface.

A) B)
Figure 7. SEM micrograph showing A) composite bars containing recycle and B) composite bars containing virgin fiber. The recycle composites have much less fiber bridging at the crack surface than those containing virgin fiber.

The virgin fiber bars and recycled bars shared similar fracture features such as those listed above as well as voids originating around the fibers which lead to fibrillar crazing. The fibrillar crazing is pointed out in Figure 8 for a composite containing recycle. However, besides these similarities major differences arise between the systems when comparing the fracture surface. The virgin bars showed a very jagged and rough fracture surface due to the matrix undergoing more plastic deformation than bars containing recycle. There are several unique crack origins that branch into each other resulting in a slower failure for the bars containing virgin fiber. However, the recycled composite bars undergo catastrophic failure rapidly, with little or no fiber bridging. Although the BMC samples with Mecerlec recycle showed good bonding between the loose fibers in the recycle and the virgin resin, bonding was poor between the resin part of the recycle and the virgin resin. The black resin, which has ~5% thermoplastic polymer mixed with the thermoset system, displayed very poor bonding to the new matrix, a distinct interface between the virgin and recycled resin at fracture surface was evident. The black resin pull-out at the surface can be seen in Figure 9. On the other hand, the recycled bars showed exceptional resin to fiber bonding. Most fiber ends showed radial cracking, as can be seen in Figure 10, a sign of high stress which would indicate matrix to fiber load transfer.

Figure 8. Fracture surface of recycled composite system showing fibrillar crazing.

Figure 9. SEM micrograph of composite containing recyclate; fracture surface exhibits large resin pull-out of black resin pieces.

Figure 10. SEM micrograph of recycled composite fracture surface showing radial cracking, a sign of high stress, which would indicate load transfer from matrix to fiber.

Fiber Content: As was mentioned earlier, there is a discrepancy in the fiber content between bars containing virgin fibers and those containing recyclate. Much of the information presented in the literature is based on recycled systems formulated using weight percents. Additionally, many papers report a direct substitution of recyclate for virgin fiber. However, the recyclate is made up of fiber, resin and filler, for our system the composition was 34 wt% fiber, 50 wt% resin, and 16 wt% filler.⁹ Therefore, a direct replacement of recyclate for filler results in a final composite that will always have a lower fiber content. Since the fiber is the reinforcing agent in the composite⁴, one would never reach strength values equaling 100% the strength of a virgin composite. To this end, a new formulation was made to include enough recyclate to have an equal amount of fiber as the bars made with virgin chopped strand. From Table 1, the virgin bars contained ~17 wt.% fiber. However, the recycled bars ended up with a fiber content of roughly 12 wt.% fiber due to difficulty in processing at higher recyclate loading. New virgin bars with 12wt.% fiber were made for comparison. Fracture surfaces for the newly formulated composites were analyzed using SEM and optical microscopy. Fiber bonding and recyclate resin bonding were scrutinized. Figure 11 shows that most of the fibers in the reformulated recyclate composite exposed at the fracture surface had good coating and surface dispersion of resin.

Figure 11. SEM micrograph of reformulated recycled composite showing resin coverage of the individual fibers.

Further SEM analysis confirmed that resin pull-out was the dominant failure mechanism for the newly formulated recycled composite. The resin pull-out was similar to that found in the bars containing direct replacement of recyclate for virgin fiber (refer back to Figure 9). The added fiber definitely created more fiber bridging during fracture but did not, however, increase the strength. This is most probably due to the dramatic increase in the amount of recyclate resin and new resin interfaces. This greatly increased the number of sites for cracks to originate and paths for the fractures to propagate, negating the increase in fiber bridging from the addition of loose fibers. The fracture surface indicated that fiber bridging is stronger than the resin-resin interface, as resin pull-out is the main cause of failure according to microscopic data. The fracture surface also exhibits some horizontal fiber pull-out and holes left from pull-out as shown in Figure 12. This is a characteristic unique for the reformulated bars. Most of the fibers in the recyclate have a random orientation, as most do not remain in strand. In Figure 13, the higher degree of fiber bridging is visible (also refer back to Figure 7). However, the major weakness of these composite bars still stems from the recyclate, namely the black resin pieces. It can be seen in Figure 14 that the failure in the reformulated recyclate bars originates on the small cross-sectional surface of the bars and propagates around the black resin pieces. In this sense, the resin pieces are acting as an impurity defect, which encourages crack branching, propagation, and eventual failure.

Figure 12. SEM micrograph of reformulated recycled composite showing horizontal fiber pull-out at the fracture surface.

C)

Figure 13. SEM micrograph of crack surface of C) newly formulated composite bars

Figure 14. Optical micrographs of two crack origins on the side of the reformulated recyclate composite bars. The crack then propagates and branches around the black resin pieces.

IV. Conclusions

The fact that samples containing both recyclate and virgin fibers showed a combination failure between the brittle failure of bars containing solely recyclate and the plastic deformation of bars containing solely virgin fibers indicates that mixing recyclate and virgin materials is a viable means of creating new composites that contain recycled materials.

In industry, one of the main reasons for the weakening of composites made with recyclate is that there is much less fiber present. The strength of glass-reinforced composites is directly proportional to the amount of fiber added. This was illustrated in the increased fiber bridging at the fracture surface for composite bars containing more fiber reinforcement. Making direct weight percent substitution of recyclate for virgin fiber is an inaccurate way to formulate the BMC. In doing so, the amount of reinforcement added to the composite is greatly decreased. One way to avoid this is to determine the amount of glass fiber in the recyclate and adjust the formulation of the BMC so that a 1 to 1 substitution of fiber for fiber is made. Despite the additional crack bridging obtained with the reformulation, the drastic increase in the amount of recyclate resin and new matrix interfaces creates more sights for cracks to originate and paths for them to propagate.

The major reason behind the weakening of these glass reinforced thermoset composites containing recyclate is poor bonding between old and new resin. Composite bars containing solely virgin materials showed high percent coating coverage of all fibers and very little matrix fracture. The significant amounts of resin pull-out at the fracture surface indicate that the resin already present in the recyclate is not wetting and bonding with the new resin during forming. The recyclate that contains small portions of thermoplastic

additives (the black resin) in particular seems to be the main source of failure and was often pulled out at fracture. We are currently investigating several surface treatments for the recyclate in order to create a strong covalent bond between recyclate resin and virgin resin.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded through the Alfred University Center for Environmental and Energy Research. I would also like to thank Dr. Jim Varner and Mr. Ward Votava for their help with the microscopy analysis.

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